

Clinical Innovation

Comparative Evaluation of the Effects of Injectable Platelet rich Fibrin & Micro needling For Gingival Augmentation in Thin Periodontal Phenotype a 3 Months Clinical Trial

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Background: The term gingival biotype refers to the thickness of the gingiva in the faciopalatal dimension, categorized as thick (≥ 2 mm) or thin (< 1.5 mm) biotype. Thin gingival biotype is a predisposing factor for gingival recessions, a common aesthetic issue in dental practice. This study aims to assess the impact of liquid injectable-platelet-rich fibrin (i-PRF) and Micro Needling (MN) on gingival thickness in individuals with thin periodontal phenotypes at different time intervals.

Materials and Methods: In this split-mouth study, 22 systemically healthy patients with thin periodontal phenotypes were randomly treated allocated to Group -A(11) where MN was done to enhance gingival thickness and Group-B(11) where i-PRF was injected at interval of 10 days in 4 sessions. Clinical periodontal measurements, GT were assessed before the treatment and every month for three months after the final injection.

Results: After the evaluation of GT between the groups at baseline, there was a non-significant difference in the gingival thickness. However, after 1st month, in Group B (i-prf) with mean value of 1.28 ± 0.09 at 1st month and mean value 1.43 ± 0.08 at 3rd month was significantly greater than group-A(MN) with mean value of 1.14 ± 0.16 at 1st month and value of 1.24 ± 0.13 at 3rd month of gingival thickness ($p < 0.001^*$)

Conclusion:

In individuals with thin periodontal phenotypes, both i-PRF and MN demonstrated the potential to increase gingival thickness. These non-surgical methods could serve as an effective initial step in managing gingival recession.

Introduction

The transformation in the field of periodontics has led to the development of newer, less invasive therapeutic approaches along with improved diagnostic methods, which allows proper evaluation and management of surrounding tissues to provide best outcome of periodontal therapy. Minimally invasive treatment helps to achieve satisfactory therapeutic results with minimum trauma to tissues of any interventional process.¹

Ochsenbein and Miller iterated the value of "thick vs. thin" gingiva in

restorative treatment planning.² A gingival thickness of > 1.5 mm is defined as thick biotype and a gingival thickness of < 1.5 mm as thin biotype. The morphologic characteristics of the gingiva depends on various factors like the dimension of the alveolar process, the form of the teeth and the eventual inclination and position of the completely erupted teeth.³

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Gingival recession is usually observed in the presence of trauma and inflammation in individuals with thin phenotypes and pocket formation in individuals with thick phenotype. The periodontal phenotype also affects the surgical technique to be selected for coverage of the root surface. It has been reported that a flap thickness of > 0.8 mm results in a covered root surface of 100%, whereas a flap thickness of < 0.8 mm results in partial root coverage in coronally advanced flap operations for Miller class I or II root coverage.⁴

The final aim of periodontal therapy is to restore the lost periodontal structure to its complete function and aesthetics. Platelet rich fibrin being a reservoir of growth factors and cytokines (transforming growth factor beta-1, insulin-like growth factor 1 and 2, platelet-derived growth factor, cytokine vascular endothelial growth factor, and interleukin 1, 4, and 6, that not only help in tissue regeneration but also accelerate wound healing.⁵ Platelets also contain biologically active proteins and the binding of these secreted proteins within a developing fibrin mesh or to the extracellular matrix can create chemotactic gradients favouring the recruitment of the stem cells, stimulating cell migration, differentiation, and promoting repair. The natural fibrin framework protects growth factors from proteolysis, so they can stay active for a longer period. This leads to an effective neovascularization and an accelerated wound closing with less post-operative infections.⁶

Microneedling (MN) is also known as “percutaneous collagen induction therapy.” Microinjuries created by MN result in minimal superficial bleedings and create a wound-healing cascade from which various growth factors, such as platelet-derived growth factors, transforming growth factors, connective tissue growth factor and fibroblast growth factors, are released.⁷⁻⁸ In MN, the tissue responds as if experiencing tissue trauma and the body's own collagen production is induced to preserve skin integrity.⁹ Growth factors are released immediately after injury, inducing the proliferation of new cells, and fibroblasts are transformed into collagen and elastin fibres from day 5 up to week 8. Fibroblasts produce collagen and elastin fibres by migrating to the point of intrusion for wound closure. Newly formed fibres thicken the tissue during a process known as neo-collagenesis. Fibroblasts also trigger neo angiogenesis by stimulating the proliferation of endothelial cells in the vessels. Tissue remodelling continues from approximately 8 weeks up to 1 year.¹⁰

The positive effects of MN and i-PRF on the biological potential, neo-angiogenesis, neocollagenesis and wound healing favour their use to improve the tissue phenotype. The aim of study is to evaluate the effects of i-PRF and MN individually on the GT of the periodontal phenotype in individuals with thin phenotypes.

Aims & Objectives

The aim of this present study is the comparative evaluation of micro needling (MN) in group-A and injecting injectable platelet-rich fibrin (i-PRF) in group-B in on gingival thickness at different time intervals.

Materials & Methods

This prospective randomized clinical trial, was conducted in the Department of Periodontology, Inderprastha Dental College and Hospital, aimed to assess 22 individuals with the impact of two interventions, Micro-needling (MN) and injectable platelet rich fibrin (i-PRF), on gingival thickness with a thin periodontal phenotype.

Patient Selection: Inclusion Criteria

No medical problems that would contraindicate routine periodontal surgery. Patients within the age group of 18-55 were selected for the study. Patients having thin gingival biotype ≥ 1.5 . Non-smokers and Patient with plaque index score < 1.0 were included in the study.¹¹

Exclusion Criteria

Smokers and tobacco chewers, Patients having Class IV gingival recession. Patients with history of chronic systemic disease, bruxism, on any immunosuppressant drugs, on antibiotic therapy in the past three months. Pregnant and lactating patients. Patients with any known allergy to drugs. Aggressive periodontitis patients. Mucosal disorders like high frenal attachments and ulcers, medically compromised patients, Patients who are under any medications that is known to influence periodontal tissues.

Treatment Groups:

Participants were randomly assigned to Group A (MN) or Group B (i-PRF). Group A received Microneedling was done using keratinized tissue, while Group B received injectable platelet-rich fibrin (i-PRF) was injected to the mucogingival margin.

Periodontal Phenotype Determination:

During the measurement of periodontal probing depth (PD), patients with a high periodontal probe visibility in the mandibular anterior teeth were identified. These patients underwent GT measurement using transgingival probing technique in the mandibular anterior teeth, and those with a measured GT of ≥ 0.8 mm (Baldi et al., 1999) were diagnosed with thin phenotype.

Data Collection Methods:

Periodontal phenotype will be assessed on the basis of Visual method, followed by Transgingival probing by using the University of North Carolina no.15 probe (UNC -15, Hu-friedy, Chicago, IL, USA) and #20 endodontic K-file with a silicone disk stop respectively. The methods used for evaluation of gingival thickness include visual assessment with aid of probe and direct measurement. For visual assessment, if UNC-15 periodontal probe, when placed into the gingival sulcus, is visible through gingival sulcus, gingival biotype is considered as thin and when periodontal probe is not visible through gingival sulcus then it is considered as thick gingival biotype.

For direct measurement of gingival thickness, a #20 endodontic K-file with a silicone disk stop was inserted trans gingivally into the anaesthetized selected site, stopper was used as the reference point and the exact measurement was recorded.

Pre-operative Phase:

Routine laboratory blood investigations were conducted. Initial phase therapy included scaling, root planing, and personalized oral hygiene instructions. Occlusal adjustments were made if trauma from occlusion was diagnosed. After 3-4 weeks, a periodontalre evaluation was done.

Clinical Parameters:

Clinical parameters, including Plaque Index (PI) (Silness&Løe, 1964)¹², Gingival Index (GI)(Loe & Silness, 1963), and Gingival Thickness (GT), were assessed at baseline (0-day pre-operative), 1 month, and 3 months post-operative.

Gingival thickness (GT): To measure GT from the apical 1.5 mm of the gingival margin, a No:15 endodontic spreader was placed in the centre of a 3-mm-diameter silicone disc. The spreader was inserted perpendicularly from the vestibular midpoint at 1.5 mm apical of the gingival margin, through the soft tissues until a hard surface was felt. The silicon disk was laid in

tight contact with the soft tissue surface. The GT measurement was made 1.5 mm apical of the gingival margin as the gingival margin overlapped with the coronal border of the silicone disc at that time. The penetration depth between the silicone disc and the spreader tip was measured (Zucchelli et al., 2010)

Preparation of i-PRF Patients were prepared by venipuncture of the antecubital vein for blood collection from the patient at the time of surgery To obtain the i-PRF, blood collection was performed using 9 ml tubes without any additive After collecting three tubes, they was placed in the horizontal centrifuge with a tube filled with water in order to maintain the balance during centrifuging for 3 minutes at 700 rpm. Upon termination of this process, two fluid layers were formed, upper being yellow fluid layer (i-PRF) while lower layer containing red blood cells. Yellow fluid layer containing i-PRF was immediately aspirated.

In the MN group- The selected site cleaned and anaesthetized with Lidocaine 10% spray, a 0.25mm (31G) x 6mm microneedle was inserted into the tissue until the hard tissue is reached. MN was carried out.

To control bleeding due to the needle tip after the procedure, a saline-soaked sponge was placed between the lip and the gingiva. Approximately 15 min later, the sponge was removed from the administration site.

In the i-PRF group- The selected site was cleaned and anaesthetized with Lidocaine 10% spray and then i-PRF was injected into the coronal region of the mucogingival margin in alveolar mucosa of the study area.

Statistical Analysis:

All statistical analyses were conducted using software (statistical package for social science) version 26.0 statistical software. Inter group statistical comparisons were assessed by the Mann-Whitney U-test. Intergroup Comparisons of % change was assessed by independent t-test followed by Mann-Whitney U-test. The Spearman's rank correlation test was used to identify relationships between GT and clinical periodontal parameters. Statistical significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

Result

GT is primary outcome parameters and clinical periodontal measurements and correlations are secondary outcome parameters of this current study. After the evaluation of GT between the groups, a very highly statistically significant difference of < 0.001 p value was found in gingival thickness between Group A

and Group B. At baseline, there was a non-significant difference in the gingival thickness of the two groups. However, after 1st month, in group A mean value of 1.14 ± 0.16 and at 3rd month mean value of 1.24 ± 0.13 of gingival thickness which is significantly greater in Group B with mean value of 1.28 ± 0.09 at 1st month and mean value 1.43 ± 0.08 at 3rd month (i-Prf group) as compared to the Group A (MN group).

Statistically significant increase was observed between all follow-up measurements compared to the baseline in both groups of all mandibular teeth, central tooth, lateral tooth and canine tooth.

Clinical Periodontal Indexes: RD level did not show any changes at any point in the study. In the intergroup comparisons, at 1st month there was no statistically significant results in PI and GI values and statistically significant difference at 3rd month in GI with p value of 0.021 and no statistically significant result in PI with p value of 0.522.

Discussion

The findings of this current investigation demonstrated that the elevations in the GT level resulting from both the i-PRF and MN treatments were statistically significant. The group that got intravenous platelet-rich fibrin (i-PRF) to enhance gingival thickness (GT) saw a statistically significant increase at the 3rd month, in comparison to the group that only received mineralized nanoparticles (MN).

The association between the periodontal phenotype and GT is greater compared to KTW and papilla height (De Rouck, Eghbali, Collys, De Bruyn, & Cosyn, 2009)¹²; (Fischer, Richter, Keschull, Petersen, & Fickl, 2015)¹³. Thus, GT was selected as the primary determining factor in this investigation. According to a paper by Kloukos et al. (2018)¹⁴, transgingival probing was found to provide satisfactory findings for measuring gingival thickness in the central teeth of the lower jaw.

Prior to the MN/i-PRF procedures and GT measurement using trans gingival probing, a topical aesthetic was applied. This was done because injecting local anaesthesia could lead to inaccurate thickness measurement due to its storage in the tissue. Additionally, the vasoconstrictor substances present in the anaesthesia could impact the distribution of i-PRF that is injected into the area.¹⁴ Typically, achieving the desired effects with MN requires many sessions. According to Alster & Graham (2018)¹⁵, undergoing 3-5 sessions of MN with intervals of 2-4 weeks resulted in a reported improvement of 50% to 70% in acne scars. In this study,

four sessions of i-PRF and MN+i-PRF were conducted with a gap of 10 days between each session. Previous research suggests that the highest amount of collagen production during wound healing occurs within 7-14 days. Additionally, the PRF resorption time is estimated to be 7-11 days, and growth factors are released from i-PRF after 10 days.

Throughout the research period, it was noted that the level of recession depth remained constant, with no occurrence of new gingival recession and no growth in existing gingival recessions. Throughout the 3-month follow-up period, there was no observed occurrence of creeping attachment. The absence of creeping attachment in this study can be attributed to the thinner connective tissue and the limited follow-up time. This phenomenon is caused by the smooth muscle characteristics and contractile activity of fibroblasts in the connective tissue. The GT values had the greatest rise in the third month after the treatment in both the i-PRF and MN groups, as a result of tissue proliferation. However, these GT levels were not considered stable due to the incomplete remodelling and maturation of the tissues.

When comparing the measures taken in the 3rd month following the treatment to the initial readings, the i-PRF group showed a 35.33% rise in GT, whereas the MN group showed a 21.11% increase. Neo angiogenesis and neocallo genesis are believed to be the reasons for reaching the greatest level of GT in the third month. When comparing GT values across the groups, a substantial difference was found in favour of the i-PRF group at the 3rd month. This difference may be related to the favourable effects of MN on long-term neo angiogenesis and neo-callogenesis (Bhardwaj, 2013).¹⁶ Furthermore, since our study of MN in dentistry juxtaposed with research that employed an MN system in dermatology. A study conducted in 2008 found that MN treatments resulted in an increase in the synthesis of collagen and elastin fibres. Additionally, the stratum spinosum layer was observed to be 40% thicker six months following the treatment. One year after an MN session, histological examinations revealed an increase in collagen and elastic fibre buildup in the reticular dermis, a thicker epidermis, and a normal stratum corneum (Aust et al., 2008)¹⁷; (Aust et al., 2010)¹⁸. A study was conducted to assess the impact of an MN procedure in addition to the application of topical vitamin A and vitamin C. The results showed that using only topical A and C led to a 22% increase in epidermal thickness, while using MN along with topical A and C

resulted in a 140% increase in epidermal thickness. These changes were observed 8 weeks after the procedure, compared to the initial measurements (Aust et al., 2011)¹⁹. Fabbrocini et al. (2011)²⁰ conducted two sessions of MN for treating wrinkles in the cervical area. According to the research, the thickness of the tissue rose by roughly 0.45 mm in the eighth month after the therapy. The results of this investigation were consistent with the findings reported in the dermatological literature, which suggest a rise in tissue thickness.

The participants' low PI and GI scores align with previous research that has compared the periodontal phenotype with PI and GI scores (Goldstein, Boyan, Cochran, & Schwartz, 2001)²¹. A correlation study was performed to examine the relationship between GT, KTW parameters, and clinical periodontal measures at baseline-1 month and baseline-3 month. The study revealed a statistically significant link among these measures, suggesting that a rise in GT is associated with a lack of inflammatory diseases.

The present study identified a statistically significant increase in GT level when using i-PRF and MN application in individuals with a thin phenotype. However, the study's major limitations lie in the absence of evaluation regarding patient reported outcomes measures (PROMs) and patient reported experience measures (PREMs). These limitations hinder a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of this novel approach in enhancing gingival width and thickness. Additional constraints include the uncertain long-term benefits for patients, the relatively small sample size of 22 participants, the restriction of i-PRF

injection only into the apical area of the mucogingival margin due to the dense structure of the keratinized tissue, and the absence of assessment of tooth positioning in the dental arch.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study sheds light on efficacy of MN and i-PRF in increasing gingival thickness. The selection criteria ensured a homogeneous participant group, and the randomized assignment minimized bias. Clinical parameters, including PI and GI, were recorded to assess overall oral health, while specific focus was placed on gingival thickness.

This trial contributes to understanding the potential benefits of MN and i-PRF in managing thin periodontal phenotypes, providing valuable insights for non-surgical interventions. Monitoring over 3 months allows assessment of both shortterm and potential sustained effects. The study design, with clear inclusion and exclusion criteria, systematic treatment groups, and rigorous clinical parameter assessments, strengthens the reliability of the findings. The results of this trial may guide future treatment approaches in addressing gingival thickness concerns in individuals with thin periodontal phenotypes. The promising effects of i-PRF and MN on GT in individuals with thin phenotypes, showcasing potential applications in periodontal health. Nevertheless, further research addressing the identified limitations is warranted to comprehensively evaluate the long term benefits and patient experiences of these interventions.

Analysis

Pre-operative picture

Transgingival probing To check thin gingival type

Measurement of Gingival thickness with file with stopper

Measuring Thickness with werner calliper

Centrifugal Machine for preparation of I-PRF

Prepared I-PRF

Micro needling under incisors

I-PRF

Base line picture of group-A(MN)

Post- Operative 12 Weeks of Group A

Pre- operative picture of Group-B

Post-operative picture of group -bat 12 weeks

Tables

Comparison of Gingival Thickness between Group A and Group B Comparison of % change in Gingival Thickness between Group A and Group B

Interval	Group	N	Mean	SD	P-Value
Baseline - 1 month	Group A	11	-10.43	7.21	0.079
	Group B	11	-21.55	17.96	
Baseline - 3 months	Group A	11	-21.11	13.87	0.025
	Group B	11	-35.33	18.84	

^y indicates Independent t test; [#] indicates Mann Whitney test; * indicates asign if I cant difference atp 0.05; -vesign indicatesan increasein the gingival thickness

From baseline to 1 month, the increase in gingival thickness (in %) of Group A did not differ significantly from that of group B. However, from baseline to 3

months, the increase in gingival thickness (in %) of Group A was significantly lesser than that of Group B.

Comparison of Plaque Index between Group A and Group B

Interval	Group	N	Mean	SD	Difference	P-Value
Baseline	Group A	11	1.78	0.49	0.01	0.969
	Group B	11	1.77	0.60		
1 month	Group A	11	0.90	0.40	0.14	0.407
	Group B	11	0.76	0.36		
3 month	Group A	11	1.07	0.30	0.12	0.522
	Group B	11	1.19	0.52		

Independent test

At baseline, after 1st month and after 3rd month, there was a non significant difference in the plaque index of the two groups.

Comparison of % change in Plaque index between Group A and Group B

Interval	Group	N	Mean	SD	P-value
Baseline- 1 month	Group A	11	50.69	13.27	0.774
	Group B	11	53.13	24.32	
Baseline- 3 month	Group A	11	31.93	39.12	0.308
	Group B	11	28.22	32.58	

[†]indicates Independent ttest; [#]indicates Mann Whitney test

From baseline to 1 month, the decrease in plaque index (in %) of Group A did not differ significantly from that of group B. Similarly, from baseline to 3 months, the

change in plaque index (in %) of Group A did not differ significantly from that of group B.

Comparison of Gingival Index between Group A and Group B

Interval	Group	N	Mean	SD	Difference	P-value
Baseline	Group A	11	1.92	0.12	-0.03	0.845
	Group B	11	1.95	0.51		
1 month	Group A	11	0.52	0.18	-0.18	0.081
	Group B	11	0.70	0.27		
3 month	Group A	11	0.93	0.22	-0.32	0.021*
	Group B	11	1.25	0.35		

Independent test; *indicates a significant difference at p < 0.05

At base line and after 1st month, there was a non-significant difference in the gingival index of the two groups. However, after 3rd month, gingival index score

was significantly greater in Group B as compared to the Group A.

Comparison of % change in Gingival index between Group A and Group B

Interval	Group	N	Mean	SD	P-value
Bseline- 1 month	Group A	11	73.15	8.12	0.046*
	Group B	11	64.28	11.15	
Baseline- 3 months	Group A	11	51.62	10.65	0.004*
	Group B	11	34.84	13.32	

Independent test

From base line to 1 month, the decrease in gingival index score (in %) of Group A was significantly greater than that of Group B. Similarly, from base line to 3

months, the decrease in gingival index score (in %) of Group A was significantly greater than that of Group B.

Graphs

References

1. Fotani S, Shiggaon LB, Alka Waghmare, Gunderao Kulkarni, Amol Agrawal, Rohit Tekwani. Effect of injectable platelet rich fibrin (i-PRF) on thin gingival biotype: A clinical trial. *J Appl Dent and Med Sc* 2019;5(2):
2. Rajpoot N, Nayak A, Nayak R, Bankur PK. Evaluation of variation in the palatal gingival biotypes using an ultrasound device. *JCDR* 2015; 9(3): Zc56.
3. Abraham S, Deepak KT, Ambili R, Preeja C, Archana V. Gingival biotype and its clinical significance—A review. *The Saudi journal for dental research*. 2014; 5(1):3-7.
4. Ozsagir ZB, Saglam E, Sen Yilmaz B, Choukroun J, Tunali M. Injectable platelet-rich fibrin and microneedling for gingival augmentation in thin periodontal phenotype: A randomized controlled clinical trial. *J Clin Periodontol*. 2020;47(4):489- 499.
5. Swetha A, Chandramohan N. Enhancing gingival biotype using the wonder liquid iPRF— a pilot study. *International Journal of Contemporary Medical Research* 2021;8(8):H5-H9
6. Richard J. Miron^{1,2} & Giovanni Zucchelli³ & Michael A. Pikos⁴ & Maurice Salama^{1,5,6} & Samuel Lee⁷ & Vincent Guillemette⁸ & Masako Fujioka-Kobayashi^{1,9,10} & Mark Bishara¹¹ & Yufeng Zhang¹² & Hom-Lay Wang² & Fatiha Chandad⁸ & Cleopatra Nacopoulos¹³ & Alain Simonpieri^{14,15,16} & Alexandre Amir Aalam¹⁷ & Pietro Felice³ & Gilberto Sammartino¹⁸ & Shahram Ghanaati¹⁹ & Maria A Hernandez¹ & Joseph Choukroun Use of platelet-rich fibrin in regenerative dentistry: a systematic review 2017 Jul;21(6):1913-1927
7. A new approach for increasing the gingival thickness by using injectable platelet rich fibrin (i-prf) – a clinical and radiographic study
8. Microneedling: A Review and Practical Guide Tina S. Alster, MD* and Paul M. Graham, DO †2018 Mar;44(3):397-404 © 2017 by the American Society for Dermatologic Surgery.
9. Microneedles and Nanopatches-Based Delivery Devices in Dentistry Panchali Batra¹, Anika Dawar², Sanjay Miglani³ 2020, Jul-Sep, 8(3): e116
10. Singh A, Yadav S. Microneedling: Advances and widening horizons. *Indian Dermatol Online J*. 2016;7(4):244- 254.
11. Loe H. The Gingival Index, the Plaque Index and the Retention Index Systems. *J Periodontol* 1967; 38:610-616
12. De Rouck, T., Eghbali, R., Collys, K., De Bruyn, H., & Cosyn, J. (2009). The gingival biotype revisited: transparency of the periodontal probe through the gingival margin as a method to discriminate thin from thick gingiva. *J Clin Periodontol*, 36(5), 428-433.
13. Fischer, K. R., Richter, T., Keschull, M., Petersen, N., & Fickl, S. (2015). On the relationship between gingival biotypes and gingival thickness in young Caucasians. *Clin Oral Implants Res*, 26(8), 865-869.
14. Kloukos, D., Koukos, G., Doulis, I., Sculean, A., Stavropoulos, A., & Katsaros, C. (2018). Gingival thickness assessment at the mandibular incisors with four methods. A cross-sectional study. *J Periodontol*.
15. Alster, T. S., & Graham, P. M. (2018). Microneedling: A Review and Practical Guide. *Dermatol Surg*, 44(3), 397-404
16. Bhardwaj, D. (2013). Collagen induction therapy with dermaroller. *Community Based Medical Journal*, 1(1), 35-37
17. Aust, M. C., Fernandes, D., Kolokythas, P., Kaplan, H. M., & Vogt, P. M. (2008). Percutaneous collagen induction therapy: an alternative treatment for scars, wrinkles, and skin. *Plast Reconstr Surg*, 121(4), 1421-1429.
18. Aust, M. C., Knobloch, K., Reimers, K., Redeker, J., Ipaktchi, R., Altintas, M. A., . . . Vogt, P. M. (2010). Percutaneous collagen induction therapy: an alternative treatment for burn scars. *Burns*, 36(6), 836-843.
19. Aust, M. C., Reimers, K., Kaplan, H. M., Stahl, F., Repenning, C., Scheper, T., . . . Vogt, P. M. (2011). Percutaneous collagen induction-regeneration in place of cicatrization? *J Plast Reconstr Aesthet Surg*, 64(1), 97-107
20. Fabbrocini, G., De Vita, V., Di Costanzo, L., Pastore, F., Mauriello, M. C., Ambra, M., . . . Monfrecola, G. (2011). Skin needling in the treatment of the aging neck. *Skinmed*, 9(6), 347-351.
21. Goldstein, M., Boyan, B. D., Cochran, D. L., & Schwartz, Z. (2001). Human histology of new attachment after root coverage using subepithelial connective tissue graft. *J Clin Periodontol*, 28(7), 657-662.